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INTEGRATING ICT IN EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: A FACILITATOR'S COMPREHENSION

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Abstract

Information and communication have played a vital role in the development of human being. In current times, modification and integration are keys to success. Technology has seen a new phase, with extensive measures being curated all around the world to facilitate the masses in one or the other form. This advancement in technology has flourished new ways through which information technology (IT) can be boosted along with communication technology (CT). The combination of IT and CT is information and communication technology (ICT). ICT means technology that provides access to information through telecommunications with primary focus on CT. In the past decades, ICT has provided society with a vast array of new communication capabilities. This technology has equipped common men with capability equal to super power as time-zone is no more a barrier for common men and they can communicate in real-time with others in distinct countries. The world has become like a global village. ICT has become part of education system as well but the education for sustainable development (ESD) still remains a major concern. The introduction of smart-classes in the schools is one such example of ICT. The learners are being taught not just orally but also with educational videos to support the motive. Also e-lectures and online classes are a boon, where a learner can attend a lecture being conducted in Canberra while sitting in India. Need is there to focus upon and to develop ICT-friendly curriculum to use ICT in learning processes in order to achieve ESD.

Key words: ICT, ESD, IT, Sustainable Development

Introduction

ICT has brought about a revolutionary, developmental and progressive change in the way society works. It plays a major role in our thinking, working as well as communication. It is one

of the fastest evolving sectors of our world and since is changing at a very rapid pace. ICT includes radio and television, as well as newer digital technologies such as computer and the internet. It has evolved as potentially powerfully enabling tools for educational change and sustainable development. The socio-economic, cultural and political transformations are necessary part for sustainable development. In this modern technological world, there has been a need to explore ICT as a part to increase these factors and ICT in education (www.elmoglobal.com) help in promoting sustainable development across the world. ICT has the potential in preparing learners for life in the 21st century. Through learning ICT skills, learners are ready to face challenges coming ahead based on proper comprehension (Grimus, 2000). As per Bransford, Brown and Cocking (2000), use of ICT can support and facilitate learners to develop the competencies required for the globalization. This is because ICT can help learners to develop their psychomotor skills, boost up their inner motivation and widen their factual knowledge and information (Grabe & Grabe, 2007; Hussain, Morgan & Al-Jumeily, 2011).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2003) uses the term ICT to explain the tools and the processes to access, retrieve, store, organize, manipulate, produce, present and exchange information by electronic and other automated modes and means. These can include, but not limited to, hardware, software and telecommunications in the terms of computers, scanners, digital cameras, phones, faxes, modems, compact disc, DVD players and recorders, digitized video, radio and television programmes, database programmes and multimedia programmes (Anderson & Dexter, 2005; Anderson, 2005). According to Tella and Adu (2010), the use of ICT in education and training only began when accessibility and availability to ICT services along with higher bandwidths had become common to most of the learners. The issue is that we attach and ascribe to new technologies the attributes of earlier existing media and accompanying educational practices without development and reflections on new and better ways to support and evaluate learning outcomes.

Information and Communication Technology

Information and communication have played an integral part in the development of human race. In today's time, modification or integration is the key to successes. Technology has seen a new phase, with extensive measures being curated all around the world to facilitate the

masses in one or the other form are humongous in nature. This advancement in technology has flourished new ways through which IT can be boosted along with CT. IT refers to the maintenance, involvement, induction and functioning of computer based soft wares and hardware that helps in achieving a targeted goal by the use of technology. The combination of both refers to ICT.

ICT refers to technologies that provide access to information through telecommunications. It is similar to IT, but focuses primarily on communication technologies. This includes the Internet, wireless networks, cell phones, and other communication mediums.

In the past few decades, information and communication technologies have provided society with a vast array of new communication capabilities. This technology has facilitated common men with capability equal to 'super power', as time-zone is no more a barrier for common men as they can communicate in real-time with others in different countries using technologies such as instant messaging, voice over IP (VoIP), and video-conferencing. Social networking websites like Facebook allow users from all over the world to remain in contact and communicate on a regular basis.

McLuhan (1962), a renowned philosopher of communication theory, said 'The World is a global village'. The possibility of calling the world a 'global village', has been possible only because of the modern ICT which empowers common men across the world with ability to communicate with others as if they are living next door. For this reason, ICT is often studied in the context of how modern communication technologies affect society.

ICT has also been part of education system. The introduction of 'smart-class' in the schools is one such example of ICT. The learners are being taught not just verbally but along with educational videos and audios to support the motive. Also e-lectures and online classes are a rage in today's time, where a learner can attend a lecture being conducted in Canberra while still being in some Indian town. Web tools, especially web 2.0 tools and OER, create a temporal-free and spatial-free environment (Kanvaria, 2014) providing maximum opportunity to all its users, whether learners, facilitators or others.

Education for Sustainable Development

According to Ayodele (2007), sustainable development can be broadly defined as the ability of the economy to support the needs of the common men of a country over a time, taking into consideration the economic, social and ecological constraints of the country. When it comes to improving the quality of life for developing nations, education has a huge role to play and sustainable development education is a key for developing our children and young common men as global citizens.

Education is the most important tool for sustainable development. Economic development in the current times is not considered to be sustainable. And thus, education and awareness to the current generations can provide to be an efficient tool towards sustainability.

Two phrases take structure: Education about sustainable development and education development and ESD. The first one deals with the teaching of what sustainability is and the latter deals with using education as a weapon for achieving sustainability. Population and resources are the two major issues which must be tackled for sustainable development and education can tackle both. Educating girl child can make her much aware about fertility and less number of offspring would lead to less use of resources.

However, it is to be noted that the most educated common men are the ones to use maximum resources leaving ecological footprints. Thus to tackle this, curriculum revaluation must be done so as to note where the loopholes are. The educational institutions act as a ground for preparing the future leaders of society with efficient skills and capabilities to bring a change in the unsustainable practices. Thus, the role of a facilitator increases from being a transmitter of knowledge to constructors and facilitators of knowledge to bring about transformation in the world. However, despite the development in technology, institutions still face issues in use of the technology in a classroom. Thus, curriculum integrated with ICT can be a powerful weapon for the facilitators as well as learner.

ICT IN EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

ICT-based techniques like modeling, social networking and concept mapping act as constructivist as well as conducive to bring about transformation. In simplest form they use multimedia to depict images, processes and pathways and complex forms use simulations and complex interactions. ICT provide an easy access to learning in formal, non-formal as well as informal sectors of the world. They encourage novel methods of interaction to facilitate not just

learning of curriculum but also choices, values and action. They promote access to educational material on sustainability via their database.

ICT not only aid in education as such but also enhance the educational experience, hence long term goals seem achievable along with short term goals (Paas, 2008). They help in enhancing learner's capacity to discern, comprehend and communicate. According to UNESCO (2003), the vision of education stresses upon a holistic, interdisciplinary approach to development of knowledge and skills required for a sustainable future as well as changes in values, behaviour, and lifestyles. Many challenges encountered by ESD can be addressed by ICT.

To use ICT in education, in fact, they must not be considered at par with the present traditional system of education which is very objective where knowledge is considered as an aspect to be instructed which limits the learner's understanding capabilities. Rather, behaviorist theories, relevant to the psychomotor skills, must be brought into the field for ESD.

ICT for ESD fall into three major classes (Paas, 2008):

Fig. 1: Major Classes of ICT for ESD

ESD means preparing learners for the upcoming challenges that the world is currently facing as well as going to face; also for new innovations and growth. A better access to such tools, applications and innovations in the field of education a better world with lots of possibilities seems possible.

Integration of ICT in ESD was first introduced by UNESCO (2003). The major objectives of this introduction were:

- The purpose shall be to promote an integrated system of research, training, information and documentation in the field of ICT in ESD. It will serve as a means of facilitating

collaboration between high-level, internationally recognized researchers and teaching staff of the university and other institutions in the world.

- The specific objectives are to investigate the present situation of ESD in facilitator education institutions in Greece and promote the integration of education for sustainable development in these institutions, with support of ICT;
- Coordinate the development of a common framework of competencies and standards of ICT in ESD among the established North-South network addressed to facilitators;
- Design and implement capacity-building by setting-up a 'training of facilitator trainers' mechanism for enhancing pre-service and in-service facilitators' skills on ICT in ESD; and
- Coordinate and conduct experiments and research on ICT in ESD in the Study programmes and facilitator practice institutions. Courses of the network's facilitator education

How to Use ICT in School Curriculum

ICT-based learning in education involves exploration, curiosity and interest which encourage learners to ask questions instead of children listening to a facilitator and repeating back information. They are actively involved in the learning process.

Geography is one of the fields where experts increasingly used ICT tools as central to the curriculum, including mapping and graphic software, Geographic Information System (GIS) and Global Positioning System (GPS). Mitchell (2007) tried to promote the development of an 'e-confident' geography department for the secondary school level. Using many geographical tools such as electronic weather stations, data projections, interactive, whiteboards, digital cameras, mobile phones, spreadsheet/ graphics software and video and photo editing software, he noted that in school, facilitator rarely used GIS (Geographic Information System) in teaching geography. Geography education community made efforts to develop the use of GIS in geography curriculum. Exploring teaching strategies as vital portion of ESD, he establishes the relationship between ESD and ICT use.

The demand for new educational approaches and ICT, in 21st century, is consistently increasing and it has the potentiality to make learning more experiential, fostering transformation

and lifelong (TERI & Dell, 2011). Moreover, the large amount of data and visuals available on any topic can be brought to the classroom from any of the corner of the world.

Makrakis (2012) shared that broader ESD themes integrated and included into the school curricula can provide a worthwhile context for ICT in education e.g. social, economic and environment issues can provide meaningful and challenging contexts for developing a vast range of ICT skills. ESD methods and strategies are conducive with constructivist and transformative learning theories, which can provide a context and rationale for using ICT-based learning tools viz. concept mapping, modeling, and social networking. When considering arenas viz. cultural diversity, intercultural understanding, health, governance, natural resources, climate change, rural development, sustainable urbanization, poverty alleviation, corporate responsibility and accountability, there is a potential to assess the impact of ICT in these key sustainable development arenas including education at large.

Conclusion

School curriculum, in general, focuses merely on the contextual knowledge and due to this contextual limitation learners do not know much about the IT, CT and their applications in education. If we use ICT for educational purposes in schools, colleges or university as a learning subject, it will enhance learner's level of understanding and achievements in other subjects. By introducing ICT in learning processes, it will also help to encourage creative, integrative teaching and learning which can ensure that learning should be focused and based on creative ideas. It is the individualized initiative directed towards various learning ways so as to achieve the goals and aims of various nations. Facilitator's capacity and knowledge has a vital role to play in sustainable development (www.learntechlib.org) for growth, development and progress of the societies and communities. They not only circulate knowledge but also create and generate new knowledge. ICT integrated teaching (Kanvaria, 2011) and professional growth of facilitators may open a new door for users for being in further contact, using technology, with their peers and experts in the field, which may lead to ESD. Their knowledge and understanding of environment help in promoting ESD. Ample provisions are needed to be made in the curriculum and subject specific syllabi for optimum utilization of ICT in schools, along with professional development of facilitators, for achieving ESD.

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